

HJRS Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities \(HEC-Recognized for 2023-2024\)](#)

Edition Link: [Journal of Academic Research for Humanities, 3\(3\) July-September 2023](#)

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Link of the Paper: <https://jar.bwo.org.pk/index.php/jarh/article/view/333>

THEMATIC AND MICROSTRUCTURE ANALYSIS OF TWITTER TWEETS: A CORPUS-BASED CDA STUDY

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Paper Information

Citation of the paper:

(APA) Iqbal, Rai, H. Parveen, Rimsha. Shah, Syed, K. (2023). Thematic and Microstructure Analysis of Twitter Tweets: A Corpus-Based CDA Study. In Journal of Academic Research for Humanities, 3(3), 259-269A.

Subject Areas:

- 1 Humanities
- 2 English Linguistics
- 3 Media Studies

Timeline of the Paper:

Received on: 03-09-2023.
Reviews Completed on: 29-09-2023.
Accepted on: 29-09-2023.
Online on: 30-09-2023.

License:

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Recognized:

Published by:

Abstract

This corpus-based research proposes critical discourse analysis based on Van Dijk's model in the text of social media. The researcher utilized a mixed method approach that found critical discourse analysis of the Twitter hashtag #we are all Pakistani on Twitter concerning the death exploration of Pakistani senior journalist Arshad Sharif. In textual analysis, based on the theoretical framework Van Dijk's model is divided into three levels microstructure, macrostructure, and Superstructure. Analyzing the Tweets, the researcher applies the microstructure in semantic, lexical, syntactical, and thematical dimensions. For data collection, a corpus of two hundred #hashtag tweets was collected randomly and the fifty most effective tweets were selected for better results interpretations. Corpus-based tweets data tagged through POC CLAWS tagger. AntConc software 3.4.4w (Laurence Anthony) is used for the analysis of semantics, syntactical, and lexical bundles. Eventually, the result shows how the language is utilized in the text to convey meanings as well as text information. It concludes that the most common language in tweets is nouns that represent people, places, things, and ideas. Lexical words are used to refer to previous information and to create unity in speech. Thematic elements in the analysis include loss, respect, death, history, injustice, grief, perseverance, public display, and the response to Arshad Sharif's death. Findings provide a better understanding of how language is used on Twitter to communicate and convey thoughts and feelings about important events. Future research may explore methods, a social cognitive approach that considers macrostructure and superstructure analysis of human rights paradigms.

Keywords: Semantic, Lexical, Microstructure, Syntactic, Tweets.

Introduction

Social media offers a simple and convenient means of discovering texts. Twitter, as a social media platform, imposes character limitations and employs hashtags to convey ideas and messages. This creates a fascinating digital communication space that enables an engaged community of communicators to share, receive, and respond to messages published on the platform. The death of Pakistani senior journalist Arshad Sharif in 2022 led to a significant outpouring of grief on social media. The hashtag #WeAreAllPakistani was widely used by Twitter users to express their condolences and solidarity with the journalist's family and colleagues. In general, critical discourse analysis (CDA) is an interdisciplinary methodology that perceives language as a manifestation of social activity, with a particular emphasis on how force, superiority, and disparity are demonstrated, replicated, and challenged via language usage and conversation in social and political circumstances [Van Dijk, \(2004\)](#) suggested that discourse analysis is a useful approach for understanding and solving problems through scientific research. It helps to uncover the underlying conditions of a problem and its resolution by analyzing the structural forms and main features of text and the relationship between concepts and ideas systematically. [Hamuddin, B. \(2012\)](#) describes discourse analysis as a methodology for explaining and analyzing how text encodes ideas and their relationships. In the context of analyzing tweets related to Arshad Sharif's death, the researcher suggests that a combination of discourse analysis, particularly written discourse analysis and CDA can provide a framework for analyzing tweets from a critical perspective. Through the examination of language usage, crucial linguistic patterns are exposed, which aid in recognizing and verifying the usage or exploitation of societal power, dominance, or opposition to power. CDA implements a three-dimensional model that includes the scrutiny of language texts, discourse practices, and excursive events can be

conceptualized as instances of social and cultural practices that help to shape the social and cultural norms or values of a particular community [Fairclough, A. \(1995\)](#). Texts incorporate vital content that serves as conduits for social interactions and hashtags also reveal a great deal about the discourse around Arshad Sharif's death in the broader socio-political context in which it occurred. The researcher focuses mainly on textual analysis using the [Van Dijk model \(2004\)](#) in the micro-structural dimension. Thus, this study explores how texts are constructed, including aspects such as word choice, discourse, and the use of linguistic devices. Van Dijk suggests that a text is more than just a collection of words, sentences, and paragraphs. Instead, it is a comprehensive discourse that conveys meaning through linguistic devices. These devices may include semantic strategies, syntactical structures, and lexical choices, among others. The paper likely aims to demonstrate how these linguistic devices work together to create meaning in texts, and how understanding these devices can help us better comprehend the messages conveyed in media. Additionally, the paper may explore how socio-cultural factors influence the construction and interpretation of texts. Overall, it seems that the paper's objective is to provide a keen understanding of text construction and how it conveys meaning, drawing on Van Dijk's linguistic, cognitive, and socio-cultural framework. The current study focuses on the problems of social media posts more specifically Twitter's tweets and the frustrating reactions of the public by applying a micro-structural approach and how the language is utilized in the text to convey meanings as well as text information and conclude thematic analysis.

Purpose of the Statement

This research mainly focuses on analyzing tweet data containing #hashtags associated with the exploration of the death of Pakistani senior journalist Arshad Sharif. The tweets were examined utilizing the framework of critical discourse analysis, as outlined by [Van Dijk](#)

(2008). By keeping in view microstructure analysis such as semantic, lexical words, phrases, sentences, and expressive vocabulary that show sad expression through text language structure in tweets against the murder of Arshad Sharif that happened in Kenya on October 23, 2022, based on these semantic, lexical principles and thematic approaches the researcher will analyze the thematic contents that provide a better understanding of how language is used on Twitter to communicate and convey thoughts and feelings about important events.

Research Objectives

- To examine the microstructure of tweets containing the #weareallpakistani hashtag contributes to the overall semantics of the discourse.
- To interpret the predominant lexical choices used in tweets with the #weareallpakistani hashtag, and how these choices reflect the underlying themes and sentiments.

Research Questions

- How does the microstructure of tweets containing the #weareallpakistani hashtag contribute to the overall semantics of the discourse?
- What are the predominant lexical choices used in tweets with the #weareallpakistani hashtag, and how do these choices reflect the underlying themes and sentiments?

Literature Review

Previous literature [Van Dijk \(2004\)](#) has explored the expressions and viewpoints shared on social media, using various analytical approaches to comprehend the impact of social media posts on social and political policies. [Baheya Jaber, \(2021\)](#) investigated critical discourse analysis of social media platforms like Twitter, such a critical social justice challenge, "honor killings," that affected women worldwide specifically in Palestine was investigated. Feminist concepts and important principles have been used as frameworks to examine issues of gender inequality, patriarchy, and oppression. The researcher applied a qualitative studies technique and performed an

important discourse evaluation of the Twitter hashtag #WeAreAllIsraaGhrayeb through the period from August 22 to September 22, 2019. Through the analysis of the tweets, 3 main subject matters emerged: the tweeters' expression of anger and frustration regarding the killing of Israa Ghrayeb, the great impact of honor killing crimes within the Palestinian community, and a strong name for justice via motion. The author, performing as a participatory movement researcher (PAR), won firsthand experiential information and deeper insights into the cultural relevance of the difficulty. This enabled the writer to cope with modern-day problems, contextualize the cultural reality, and expand a strategic motion plan geared toward bringing approximately social trade and fostering a just society, ultimately reaping rewards for the stakeholders who've witnessed the horrors of honor killing ([Jaber, 2021 & Iqbal et al., 2023](#)). According to [Bouvier \(2015\)](#), in the article titled "What was a discourse approach to Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, and other social media: connecting with other academic fields?", the author explored the concept of a discourse approach to social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, and YouTube, and emphasized the importance of connecting this approach with various academic disciplines. The article suggested that researchers could use this as a foundation to focus on areas where ambiguities of identity and culture were present in new ways due to changing cultural values about social structure, knowledge, and civic spheres ([Bouvier, 2015, p. 149](#)). In the review of the thesis by [Aljarallah \(2017\)](#), Arizona State University was titled "A Critical Discourse Analysis of Twitter Posts on the Perspectives of Women Driving in Saudi Arabia. The issue of women driving is still a big topic of discussion in Saudi Arabia, especially with the recent development sparking controversy and controversy on social media platforms like Twitter. This study explores the success of discourse around female drivers by looking specifically at the interaction between gender, through the a

analysis of tweets and hashtags. This study explores two negative theories through a literature review using Norman Fairclough's framework. Another [Emi Sahmeni \(2019\)](#) study uses van Dijk's critical discourse analysis model to unmask mass media discourse in media discourse studies. The researchers aimed to explore how Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) was employed to reveal covert ideologies and investigate power dynamics in media discourse studies. The research involved a review of sixteen journal articles, which examined the methodologies utilized to uncover social phenomena and authenticate social actor identities. The findings indicated that CDA has been widely employed to expose ideologies that marginalize oppressed groups while presenting a favorable image for those in positions of authority. Notably, Teun Van Dijk's theory emerged as one of the most frequently utilized frameworks for unmasking media profiling, encompassing three key elements: Macrostructure, superstructure, and microstructure. The study further revealed the significant role played by mass media in shaping trust, prejudice, and exerting dominance within social contexts ([Sahmeni & Afifah, 2019, pp. 39-45](#)). [Daniel Gray's \(2019\)](#) thesis study constituted a vital virtual sociology observation that tested discourse on Twitter during International Women's Day 2017 (IWD2017) using an innovative method. The primary locating of this research pertained to methodology, demonstrating the opportunity and productivity of combining qualitative analysis and 'large statistics mainly, a big quantity of tweets at the same time as maintaining the specific and precious aspects of crucial, idea-informed qualitative evaluation. The analysis exposed numerous noteworthy findings, which include the utilization of both famous and 'fringe' hashtags to attach mainstream and proper-wing reactionary topics, the superiority of anti-feminism and anti-Islam sentiments among supporters folks President Donald Trump, the division of feminism and feminists into contrasting categories within anti-

feminist discourse, and the illustration of women employing Twitter money owed related to the police and military. Methodologically, this thesis offered a complete account of the sensible considerations, demanding situations, and strategies used in approaching large social media statistics from a critical researcher's angle, emphasizing the significance of retaining previous theoretical, analytical, and ethical frameworks when enticing with such statistics ([Gray, 2019](#)). The analysis of the media coverage of court decisions on sexual violence provides important insights into the situation previously described. This work explores the main themes and social struggles behind two high-profile sexual assaults in Ireland and Spain: the #IBelieveHer movement and the #YoTeCreo movement. Analyzing the views of media, the main hashtags on Twitter, and the speech patterns of the two media outlets, this study shows that the legal interpretation of sexual violence is widely discussed in the Spanish print media, while the Spanish movement takes it out and explains the path of women on Twitter. In contrast, #IBelieveHer taps into a narrower focus and "artistic" side, providing a more personal, less interactive, and ultimately more interactive social and print media experience ([Prendergast & Quinn \(2021\)](#)). A study by [Bouvier & Machin \(2021\)](#) entitled "What is missing in the Twitter hashtag 'stop culture'? Attaining racists reveals some limits of social justice". Twitter campaigns for those who make racist or xenophobic comments are seen as helpful as they promote public action against all forms of racism and expose the failure of major organizations to address social justice issues. However, there are concerns about social media such as Twitter, which often displays hatred, moral outrage, a lack of nuance, and rudeness, thus affecting the representation of various issues. This study aims to explore how racism and xenophobia are expressed in these hashtags. The findings show that these movements affect the importance of people's racial identity and lead to a breakdown in critical understanding of these events that are

supposed to show racism (Bouvier & Machin 2021). Frame Analysis Guzman (2016) posits that Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) recognizes the fundamental principle that we perceive the world through a set of mediated lenses or frames and emphasizes that discourse is responsible for "ideological work. Both CDA and Frame Analysis recognize that journalists, and consequently media organizations, construct, maintain, and disseminate discourses to shape public opinion by presenting critical events and social actors in specific ways. Recently, frame analysis has been adapted to study feminist Twitter hashtag campaigns, such as Kim's (2017) examination of feminist activism against misogyny in South Korea and Lommel, Schreier, & Fruchtmann's (2019) exploration of the collective identity framing of US women's groups on strike. To facilitate the examination of social media platforms, the collective action framing approach Benford & Snow (2000) initially utilized to scrutinize in-person social movements has been modified. This approach was used to analyze the dominant frames in individual tweets and newspaper articles rallying around #DayWithoutWomen in May 2017. The inductive approach involved repeatedly reading individual tweets and newspaper articles to identify dominant frames for micro-level analysis. These frames were then tallied and compared to identify trends over the examined period. This study had two key analysis phases. These two phases analyzed a sample of news media and social media responses. In Salma's (2018) study titled "Van Dijk Research: Objectives of Scientific Research", the authors summarize the goals of critical analysis. Critical discourse analysis (CDA) was used not only as research but also as scientific research. Guiding questions using the method include: Is the text suitable for this type of text? Who is the author of this book? Who is the audience? Does everyone interpret the text the same way? What is the purpose behind its production? Can it be written differently? What is missing in this text? What kind of relationship do these letters show? If there is a conflict

between these articles, how do you resolve it? The purpose of the study was to exchange how recommendations for patient diets and safety had been defined in research magazine articles and institutions for high blood pressure disease. A good way to trade the discourse and remove information through association hints, the have a look at addressing the choice, generalization, deletion, and constructing methods. The Van Dijk macrostructure model of discourse was applied as a device through the researcher to conduct an essential discourse analysis of the tips given with the aid of the research articles and institutions. Excel and AntConc were also used to analyze the data collected from articles and other online sources. The examination used hints from 3 important scientific societies in addition to a complete of 10 studies articles. For extra knowledge, statistics are provided in tables and charts. The effects of the have look at showed that institutions take part in this hobby due to the fact they may be not able to offer a comprehensive discourse due to several restrictions.

Theoretical Framework

As noted earlier, Van Dijk, (2004) Critical Discourse Analysis encompasses a range of approaches, each with its own unique theoretical and analytical perspectives. The critical analysis of news articles or classroom instruction, for example, differs significantly from the analysis of everyday conversation. As a result, scholars of critical discourse analysis frequently employ specialized terminology and encompass the intricacies of their analytical frameworks. Researchers use terms such as "hegemony," "class," "race," "gender," "dominance," "discrimination," "ideology," "power," "institutions," "interests," "reproduction," "social order," and "social structure". The author will examine several foundational concepts and develop a theoretical framework that critically examines the interplay between discourse, community, and mental cognition.

Micro vs. macro

Language utilization, communication, and verbal exchanges are all elements of the microlevel of social structure. On the other hand, power imbalances, disparity, and superiority among societal groups are macro and micro-level phenomena that demand a distinct analytical approach. Critical discourse analysis aims to bridge the divide between these two levels of analysis, recognizing that the micro-macro dichotomy is a socially constructed distinction. [Alexander, J. C. \(Ed.\). \(1987\).](#) To achieve a unified critical analysis, one must adopt specific strategies for analyzing both levels simultaneously, as follows:

Members & Groups

Individuals who utilize language partake in communication within diverse social circumstances and frequently have membership in numerous social groups, institutions, or organizations. Conversely, these groups may also function through their members, influencing their communication styles and language usage.

Actions & Process

The actions of individuals within society are integral components of broader social processes and collective actions, including but not limited to the creation of news, the establishment of laws, and the spread of discriminatory attitudes or behaviors.

Context and Social Structure

Discourse and interactions are crucial components of social structure. For example, a press conference can be viewed as a distinct practice that is associated with organizations and media institutions. Hence, both narrower and broader contexts are intricately linked and constrain language usage.

Power as Control

A fundamental concept in critical discourse analysis is strength, particularly the institutional and social power held by different groups. To simplify this intricate social and philosophical analysis, we can delineate social power in terms of control. In essence, this implies that the groups that wield the most dominant discourse possess the most extensive ability to impact the views

and conduct of others. To streamline these intricate associations, research employing critical discourse analysis can center on three fundamental inquiries: How do dominant groups manage public discourse? How does this discourse mold the cognition and conduct of marginalized groups? And what are the societal ramifications of such control, such as the prolongation of social inequalities?

Power and Access

Power can be categorized into two categories: social power and power abuse. Social power alludes to the authority that one group possesses over another, whereas power abuse signifies that this control is exercised in favor of the dominant group. Members who occupy a position of dominance within social groups can exert significant influence, such as control over language use and written communication, due to their powerful social or institutional positions or roles. The management and accessibility of discourse are closely tied to social power. Dominance through language involves having privileged access to language and context, which functions as a form of power like other social resources like wealth, income, job status, knowledge, and education. Therefore, while ordinary individuals may exercise active control over discourse genres, such as casual conversations with acquaintances, they may only wield more passive control over institutional language use. For example, politicians wield authority over governmental and parliamentary dialogue and enjoy privileged access to mass media platforms. Academics govern scholarly discourse, which encompasses textbooks, curricula, and scholarly articles. Reporters dominate mass media conversation and receive exclusive admission to other authorized modes of linguistic expression, such as press conferences, press releases, and reports. By giving the research limitations, the current researcher found that there is no textual analysis of the micro-structural model in social media in Pakistan, which is why the researcher chose this topic. Besides this, the study can cover the other two dimensions of [Van Dijk's \(2004\)](#) model of

macrostructure or superstructure text analysis. This study is not based on huge amounts of data, and the results according to the current researcher may not be generalized, but this study is a positive contribution to the research being conducted on social networking, such as YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, email data, Viber, Skype, LinkedIn, and LinkedIn Corporation software.

Research Methodology

In this study, the researcher uses a mixed-methods design based on [van Dijk's \(2004\)](#) model of critical discourse analysis of the Twitter hashtag #we are all Pakistani on Twitter between October 23 and November 23, 2022. The qualitative design allowed the researcher to explore the language used in context for keen observation and understanding of meaning in each text. The quantitative design gives objective measures and sets patterns in the case of a large sample of text to determine the findings systematically. This research is applied to CDA, which focuses on the socio-cognitive approach that was proposed by Van Dijk (2004). In this approach, van Dijk combines the three dimensions of discourse: text, social cognition, and social context. ([Eriyanto, 2001, p. 224](#)). To perform textual analysis, VD also divided the text into three levels: macrostructure, superstructure, and microstructure. In analyzing the tweets, the researcher used the micro stage; microstructure is the text meaning, which can be analyzed through the different sections of words, their meanings, sentences, or vocabulary used that were tweeted by various Pakistani tweeters. Through vocabulary (lexical style), words, phrases, and sentences, tweets show anger, sadness, or frustration against the murder of journalist Arshad Sharif, and theoretical principles are used to analyze thematic content. As part of obtaining CDA, we also investigated the tweets to determine what direct or indirect messages were dropped via tweets and whether these posts supported or negated the murder crimes. An open coding sheet is used for the most salient theme categories to show major thematic content.

Data Collection

To accomplish this, Twitter posts (tweets) containing the #hashtags were collected. It should be noted that Twitter's automated software tools do not allow the collection of tweets that are more than two weeks old. The primary type of data (not collected from formal curatorial activity between participants) is used to collect a representative dataset by using an advanced search to seek information about users and responses to the hashtag and its sub-hashtag in English. By utilizing advanced search options, only tweets composed in the Pakistani language were retrieved to create the corpus for this research. It should be noted that only tweets were chosen for this study, not their respective tweet replies.

Data compilation

A corpus of two hundred hashtag #Tweets was collected randomly, and fifty of the most effective tweets were selected for better result interpretations during the period between October 23 and September 23, 2022. Corpus-based tweet data is used, which is tagged through POC CLAWS taggers that are refined by removing all the symbols and emojis from tweets, except for the full stop (.) and question mark (?). AntConc software 3.4.4w (Laurence Anthony) is used for lexical bundles. However, tweet replies were used in determining tweets written for mockery purposes.

Results & Discussion

In this major part of the study, the research questions of the study are addressed. It is worth noting that Van Dijk's model was employed to analyze the text to respond to these research questions.

The Dimension of the Text: Microstructure

The aspect of the text being analyzed is the microstructure dimension, which can be further analyzed in terms of semantic, syntax, stylistic, and rhetorical aspects. In the current study, the researcher's focus is on the semantic and lexical dimensions of microstructure analysis, as described in the following table. Corpora collected from Twitter are made part of the

research, and the details of a corpus are as follows.

Table 1.

Corpus detail

Tweets Duration	Number of Tweets	Word Tokens	Word Types
23 Oct–23 Nov 2022	200	2875	620

Table 2

Semantic	Occurrences	Frequencies	Percentage
Noun(NN1,NN2)	289	713	49.57%
Pronoun	70	73	12.00%
state verb	122	86	20.92%
Preposition	102	93	17.49%
Total	583	965	99.98%

Syntactic Cohesion

Semantic Analysis

Conjunction 37
Results 100%

Few conjunction words that link one sentence to other sentences, e.g., but or.

Discussions

Discussions on Question 1

Based on the tweet data that was analyzed using AntConc software, the following interpretations were made according to the microstructure model of van Dijk:

Noun (NN1, NN2): The most frequent type of word in the given data is a noun (NN1, NN2), with a total of 713 occurrences, accounting for 49.57% of all words. Nouns are important in conveying semantic information in tweet data as they represent people, places, objects, and ideas. There are 73 occurrences of pronouns, accounting for 12% of all words. Pronouns are used to refer to people or things already mentioned in the discourse and can be used to establish cohesion by connecting sentences or referring to earlier information. State verb: There are 86 occurrences of state verbs, accounting for 20.92% of all words. State verbs are used to describe a state or condition of mental attitude towards the death of Arshad

Sharif rather than doing an action and can be important in conveying the speaker's attitude or perspective on the topic being discussed. There are 93 occurrences of prepositions, accounting for 17.49% of all words. Prepositions are used to indicate the relationship between two words or phrases and are often used to convey spatial or temporal information. The data includes 37 occurrences of conjunctions, which are used to connect sentences and establish cohesion within a text. Overall, the data suggests that the language used in the text is primarily focused on conveying semantic information using nouns, with a significant proportion of state verbs and prepositions also being used. Cohesion is established using conjunctions to link sentences together.

Table 3

Lexical categories

No	Words categories	Vocabulary words or phrases Analyze
1	Condolence words	so sad, rest in peace, heartbreaking news, sorrowful day
2	Acknowledgment word	Brother, you were brave, a 2022 hero, a Brave man exposing,
3	Seeking absolution	May his soul rest in peace. martyred
4	Expression of sympathy	We always miss you, sir, and we will never forget your struggles. You were great. My favorite media personality Arshad Sharif was the pride of the nation. Loyalty to blood in his nation
5	Frustrated words	Planned assassination, torture, abducting, and sexually assaulting senators. Mofa and others, please stop telling us the official lie. Pakistani people are cowards. These thieves and the runaway Sharif family are a big slap on the independence of journalism.
6	Sorrowful words	My heart is so sad; I am mentally, physically, emotionally, and spiritually not ready and stable to witness this. I lost a friend, my husband, and my favorite journalists. Oct. 23, 2022. This is embarrassing and will be lost forever.
7	Future-oriented remarks	May Allah give patience to his family, sacrificing an award for her mother.
8	Praising quotes	We want Tamgh-i-Imtiaz for Arshad Sharif.

Discussions on Question Number 2

Thematic Contents

Vin Dijk's CDA theory principles focus on analyzing the basic lexical categories of Twitter posts about the death of Pakistani senior journalist Arshad Sharif, the themes and discourse structures in texts investigated, and how these are used to convey power, ideology, and social relationships. Using this framework, we can identify the following thematic contents in the vocabulary words, as given below:

Theme of Loss

So sad. Rest in peace. Heartbreaking news. A sorrowful day:

These condolence words express grief and sympathy for Arshad Sharif's death by the Pakistani public, who passed away on October 20, 2022, in Kenya. The themes of loss, sadness, and mourning are prominent in these expressions.

Theme of Honor

Brother, you were brave, a 2022 hero, a brave man exposing, and we want Tamgh-i-Imtiaz for Arshad Sharif:

These acknowledgments and praising quotes and words recognize and praise Arshad Sharif for his bravery and heroism. These words express admiration and praise for a person's achievements or qualities. The themes of excellence, recognition, and honor are prominent in these expressions. The themes of courage, honor, and sacrifice are prominent in these expressions.

Theme of Mortality

May his soul rest in peace, martyred; may Allah give him a high rank in Jannah.

Seeking absolution is a word that expresses a desire for forgiveness or spiritual peace for Arshad Sharif, who has passed away, often in the context of a tragic or violent event. The themes of mortality, justice, and redemption are prominent in these expressions.

Theme of Legacy

We always miss you, sir, and we will never forget your struggles. You were great. Media's favorite personality. Arshad Sharif was the pride of the nation. Loyalty to blood in his nation.

Expressions of sympathy express admiration and respect for a victimized Arshad Sharif who has passed away, often in the context of their contributions to society or culture. The themes of legacy, honor, and national pride are prominent in these expressions.

Theme of injustice

Planned assassination, torture, abducting, and sexually assaulting senators. Mofa and others, please stop telling us the official lie. Pakistani people are cowards. These thieves and the runaway Sharif family are a big slap on the independence of journalism. These frustrating words express anger, frustration, and disillusionment with political or social conditions. The researcher evaluates the themes of injustice, social power, abuse, honor killing, corruption, and powerlessness that are prominent in these expressions.

Theme of Grief

My heart is so sad; I am mentally, physically, emotionally, and spiritually not ready and stable to witness this. I lost a friend, my husband, and my favorite journalists. October 23, 2022: This is embarrassing and lost forever.

These sorrowful words express deep sadness and emotional pain in response to the personal or collective loss of journalist Arshad Sharif's family, friends, and all near and dear ones. The themes of grief, nostalgia, and longing are prominent in these expressions.

Theme of Resilience

May Allah give patience to his family, sacrificing an award for her mother.

These future-oriented remarks express hope, faith, or optimism about the future for his family and his mother, often in the context of a difficult or trying situation. The themes of resilience, endurance, and perseverance are prominent in these expressions.

Conclusion

This mixed method study's quantitative results have been shown in Table 1 Table 2 and Table 3 a thematic & Microstructure Analysis of Twitter Tweets: a corpus-based CDA Study by applying [Van Dijk's model \(2004\)](#). Van Dijk suggests that the text can be analyzed

independently from the context in which it was produced, but it can still influence the reader's thoughts and actions. The text has been broken down into microstructure, and for this study, the microstructure dimension was analyzed, specifically the parts of speech (POS) at the word level and the lexical analysis of the vocabulary used. The most common language in tweets is nouns that represent people, places, things, and ideas. Words are used to refer to previous information and to create unity in speech. State verbs are used to express the speaker's attitude or opinion on a subject, while verbs are used to express the relationship between people and their perspective on a specific topic. Thematic elements in the analysis include loss, respect, death, history, injustice, grief, perseverance, public display, and the response to Arshad Sharif's death. These findings provide a better understanding of how language is used on Twitter to communicate and convey thoughts and feelings about important events. This was done to enhance the persuasiveness of the text and gain support from readers. Thus, the text was not solely about the #hashtag, but rather, it discussed the government's decision-making. The #hashtag served as a tool to convey the writer's message and make it more socially relevant, attracting public attention and encouraging interaction. In the previous discussion, Aljarallah's (2017) findings and analysis of Twitter data with van Dijk's micro-structural model revealed key points regarding the death of Pakistani senior journalist Arshad Sharif. For Future recommendations, research may explore other two dimensions with their related methods, such as the social cognitive approach that considers macrostructure and superstructure and in-depth analysis of human rights paradigms.

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